

PRESENT AND FUTURE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR MARINE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article gives a brief account of the current use of polymeric composite materials in the marine industry. Advantages of using composites are highlighted and their present diverse applications exemplified. Areas of future composite materials development, characterisation and processing are presented and key factors identified which need to be overcome for sustained widespread acceptance and growth of composite materials in the marine industry.

Keywords: marine, composite materials, applications

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of organic matrix composites (OMC) for marine applications started in the late 1940s. Over the years, slow but steady growth and acceptance of OMC for construction of smaller surface vessels took place. Their greater use for construction of large commercial ships, naval vessels and offshore structures is yet some time away. Ship designers and builders are not familiar with the new materials, they must develop composite technologies specifically for marine applications to exploit the benefits of composites. Once factors such as cost, weight and performance grow more important the current barriers will be challenged and overcome before affordable design alternatives to conventional marine materials (steel and aluminium) become a reality.

Compared with traditional marine materials there are various advantages that make composites attractive for use in marine structures ¹.

For surface ships, submarines and for offshore structures there is increasing demand for high strength and light weight construction where composite materials can offer weight reduction of up to 25-50% in comparison to aluminium and steel. Composites have excellent corrosion resistance which reduces maintenance, low thermal conductivity, they are non-magnetic and when damaged, glass reinforced plastic (GRP) structures are found easy to repair.

GRP composites have lower modulus of stiffness than aluminium which makes them suitable for use in ship superstructures where interaction with the hull is a problem. Composite materials can be modified to become radar absorbing thus enhancing their stealth capability. Their sonar transparency makes them ideal materials for sonar domes. Composites are easily fabricated into neat monolithic structures with minimal number of joints.

2. PRESENT MATERIALS AND APPLICATIONS

In this section a brief description of most commonly used reinforcing fibres, resins and core materials in marine fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) structures is presented including some noted applications. Detailed information on the subject is covered elsewhere ¹⁻⁴.

2.1. Mineral and Polymeric Fibres

Glass fibre is inexpensive and by far the most widely used mineral reinforcement in marine FRP construction. It has good strength to weight characteristics and is found to exhibit good chemical resistance. E-glass is the most common reinforcement which shows good strength properties and resistance to water degradation, however, over long periods of time the strength may deteriorate. S-glass reinforcement exhibits about one third higher strength than E-glass and demonstrates better fatigue resistance but the cost is significantly higher ¹.

Polymeric aramid fibres have low weight, high tensile strength and modulus, impact and fatigue resistance but relatively poor compressive performance. Ultraviolet exposure can cause degradation as can water absorption. They are difficult to cut and wet-out during lamination.

Carbon fibres possess the highest strength and stiffness. They have outstanding high temperature performance and unlike glass and aramid fibres, they are not subject to stress rupture and stress corrosion. High cost is limiting their greater use in FRP structures, however, carbon fibres are selectively used, often hybridised with glass or aramid fibres, to achieve desired stiffness.

Extended chain polyethylene fibres exhibit high strength/modulus, slightly better than aramid at ambient temperature but at elevated temperature performance falls off ².

2.2. Resins

Thermosetting resins such as polyesters, vinyl esters, epoxies and, to a lesser extent phenolics, are almost exclusively used as organic matrices in reinforced plastics for marine application ¹⁻³.

Unsaturated polyester resins (orthophthalic and isophthalic) have by far the most widespread use in the marine industry. Orthophthalic polyester has lower thermal stability, chemical resistance and processability characteristics than isophthalic polyester which has also better mechanical properties.

Vinyl esters are more expensive than polyesters but perform better showing superior corrosion resistance, hydrolytic stability and excellent physical properties such as impact and fatigue resistance. They are used to resist blistering in marine laminates often observed with polyesters. However, vinyl esters will suffer yellowing and chalking when exposed to solar radiation.

Epoxies show the best performance characteristics of all the resins used in marine industry. High cost and handling difficulties limit their use for large marine structures.

Phenolic resins are becoming attractive to the marine industry because of their good fire performance and the recently developed cold-cure process suitable for use in contact moulding of structural laminates.

Reinforced thermoplastics have some attractive features including no exotherm upon cure, which has plagued filament winding of extremely thick sections with thermosets, and enhanced damage tolerance. Thermoplastics are potentially suitable candidates for recycling.

2.3. Core materials

Core materials, such as balsa, polyvinyl chloride (PVC), and syntactic foams, are often used in conjunction with thin high stiffness and strength GRP skins as an alternative construction material, to stiffened single skin structures, for ship hulls, decks and bulkheads, offshore platforms and pressure hulls of submersible crafts ^{1,2}.

Balsa core exhibits excellent stiffness and bond strength and is frequently used as a marine grade structural core material. End-grain balsa will absorb more resin than the closed cell foam and is subject to water ingress.

PVC expanded (closed-cell linear or crosslinked) foam is used in marine sandwich construction in a density range from 45-200 kg/m³. Linear PVC foam possesses lower mechanical properties and is more ductile than the crosslinked version. Generally, they offer good resistance to water permeation, exhibit good electrical and thermal insulation including vibration and acoustic damping characteristics. At elevated temperature (40-60°C) their compressive and shear moduli are reduced.

Syntactic foam is basically a mixture of hollow glass microspheres dispersed in an epoxy or phenolic resin. It is used as a pourable and *in-situ* curable, high-viscosity fluid mass. Cured foam has low density and good physical properties.

2.4. Applications

The most significant naval application of composites has been in mine counter measure vessels (MCMVs) which require low magnetic signature and resistance to high levels of shock loading. Three basic types of hull construction are currently used ^{1,2}. For example, the hull of the U.K. *Sandown* is frame stiffened GRP construction using E-glass reinforcement and isophthalic polyester resin. The hull of the Italian *Lerici* consists of a thick monocoque GRP shell (without any longitudinal or transverse stiffeners). The decks and bulkheads are of stiffened GRP construction. In the Swedish *Landsort* and the Australian minehunter inshore (MHI) the hull is made of GRP/foam sandwich using closed cell PVC ⁵.

Other examples of GRP/foam sandwich construction include fast patrol boats (Swedish *TV 171* and *CG 29* Class vessels and the Danish *Stanflex 300*) and recently developed stealth vessel, the Swedish surface-effect-ship (SES) *Smyge*. The French *La Fayette* Class frigate has a GRP sandwich superstructure (using balsa core) fitted to a steel hull ⁶. Stiffened single skin GRP laminates have been widely used for submarine casings because of weight savings and non-corrosive properties.

In the commercial marine industry FRP construction contributes to weight and labour cost reduction, long-term trouble free performance and economic factors which affect running cost. For example, small GRP fishing boats (<25 m in length) benefit from weight and maintenance reduction resulting in increased hull life. Recently, Japan has introduced bigger FRP fishing boats with hull sizes up to 45 m in length ¹. A high speed, 244 passenger SES ferry, which operates in Norway is an air cushioned vehicle structured entirely of GRP/sandwich construction ⁷.

Commercial submersibles, for operation at moderate and extreme depths, minimise structural weight using FRP and foam cores as buoyancy materials. Combination of these materials was found to resist fatigue and impact loads including buckling failure in combination with creep effects. The French manned submersible, *Nautilie*, reached the Titanic site at 6,000 m depth ².

For offshore hydrocarbon production, composite materials provide corrosion resistant light-weight structures. It is estimated that annual offshore world consumption of composites is 30,000 tons per year. North Sea platforms alone require an estimated 6,000 tons/year, equivalent to ~7% of the total structural weight ⁸.

In the recreational and sporting sector carbon and aramid fibres, as two high-strength alternatives to fibreglass, add flexibility in laminate design, minimise weight of hulls and spars and enable construction of ultra-high performance power and sail racing boats. The prestige in the World racing events overrides all materials and fabrication costs. Some designs stretch current technology to the limit and thus provide valuable data on materials performance and design technology useful in other marine applications.

Almost all racing powered boats employ advanced hybrid composites for enhanced performance and driver safety. The driver safety cell, constructed of carbon and aramid fibres and aramid honeycomb core, is reported to withstand a 30 m drop test without serious damage. In the offshore racing circuit in 1978, power boats constructed with aramid fibre reinforcement won 8 out of 10 races. In the racing yachts class, design complexity, composite materials and construction technology play a major part in big events such as the Whitbread Round-the-World Race ^{1,4} and America's Cup competition. For competition canoes and kayaks the use of polyethylene fibre reinforcement results in overall 40% lighter product to that made with aramid fibre reinforcement ².

Other marine FRP applications include floats and buoys, oil and water tanks and various non-primary ships' fittings such as shipboard ventilation ducting, piping systems and hatch covers ³.

3. FUTURE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Future advances, which will contribute to wider acceptance and growth of composites in the marine industry, are expected in the area of materials development and evaluation, design and engineering including economic and environmental factors.

3.1. Materials Development

Physical and mechanical properties of composite materials have not been fully characterised for the range of available reinforcements, resins and core materials combinations as a result of continuing development of these and new materials. For marine applications, additional factors including environmental effects (wave loading, water uptake, temperature extremes, solar radiation, corrosion and long-term durability) on material properties require continued materials development and evaluation due to increasing performance demands on FRP materials.

Advanced composites, composed of thermoset resins and high performance fibers (aramid, carbon or polyethylene), have created new applications areas which require light-weight structures with superior mechanical properties. However, further technological improvements (eg. phenolics) and assessments are needed to characterise their response to service conditions such as long-term exposure to sea water, long-term static and cyclic fatigue, impact and fire resistance.

Reinforced thermoplastics have recently been investigated for large scale production of structural components ². Key areas, currently under development, are processability, strength and compatibility with reinforcement materials.

Sandwich construction, used in high-performance craft, offers good out-of-plane flexural properties achieved at relatively low weight. Future research and development will focus on fire hazards, non-destructive testing (NDT) and mechanical performance behaviour that differs to that observed for solid beams and panels. Experience in using sandwich construction is still relatively limited ².

Stealth requirement for naval applications will be an important future issue. FRP materials can satisfy physical and chemical requirements through structural shaping and addition of radar absorbing material to the matrix thus minimising radar signature. Additionally, in combination with infrared absorbing paint and with non-magnetic and vibration damping characteristics, composites have potential to significantly reduce the observability index ⁹.

Smart or intelligent materials are functionally responsive composites which contain various sensors that can monitor several parameters simultaneously over the entire lifetime of the structure. Composites are particularly suited for these applications because it is possible to attach or embed sensors and actuators during manufacture¹⁰. Applications may include marine structural monitoring such as strain and temperature, vibration control, stiffness and shape control etc. Such materials could also augment NDT techniques and enable structural damage assessment. In-service structural

performance data could provide invaluable information to designers in optimising structural design and safety factors.

In recent years alternative composites have started to emerge but at present with very limited applications in marine use. They are metal matrix composites (MMC) and ceramic matrix composites (CMC) which in specific cases, such as high temperature operation and very high specific compressive strength requirement, outperform OMC ¹. Production costs, however, are very high.

3.2. Physical Properties

The fire and toxicity performance characteristics of composites, which have vital safety implications, are currently the most important issues. At present, the industry is in the process of standardising the tests that can quantify composite materials performance in a fire. US Navy has taken an initiative to certify materials for use in submarines ¹¹. The commercial sector, related to small passenger and cargo vessels, is covered by general restrictions while large passenger vessels built or converted after 1984 must meet rules laid down by SOLAS (Safety Of Life At Sea) ².

The performance of FRP composites under extreme fire conditions is currently the subject of intensive research. Composites are already found to limit heat transmission to surrounding areas and, in an appropriate configuration, they have a slow rate of burn-through in hydrocarbon fires ¹. Phenolic laminates and core materials possess outstanding fire resistance and retention of mechanical properties at elevated temperature. Current limitations of phenolics are relatively poor mechanical performance, high void content, water absorption, compatibility with sizing on glass fibre reinforcement and handling difficulties such as mixing and fibre wet-out.

Future development may introduce various fire barrier treatments which function either by reflecting radiant heat back toward the heat source or by delaying heat penetration by their insulative and ablative properties. In addition, relationship of small scale fire tests to real fire scenarios requires additional study in order to sub-scale screening and modelling and save time and cost, vs. performing full-scale tests on large components like masts, stacks, deckhouses, weapons enclosures, doors and hatches, bulkheads, stanchions, ladders, tanks, foundations, etc. Presently, the optimum solution appears to be offered by hybrid GRP/steel construction thus combining the strength and stiffness retention of steel framing in a fire with the insulating characteristics offered by GRP composite laminate.

For thick laminates (single skin or GRP/sandwich) the ultrasonic technique becomes less effective as the beam is attenuated by voids. Visual examination and the "old reliable" coin taping technique may reveal delaminations or debonding in GRP structures, however, they are not reliable methods for detecting fabrication faults and service damage in thick GRP laminates and foams (PVC, syntactic) in GRP foam sandwich structures. Several NDT techniques are currently being considered ¹ (ie. thermography, modal analysis, medical X-ray computed tomography) out of which a COMSCAN, a backscatter X-ray imaging technique based on Compton scattered radiation, is possibly the most promising method for detecting defects in foams in shipboard/shipyard situations. At present, the depth of examination is limited ¹².

Although in-service marine FRP materials show good environmental stability, some effects (water, solar radiation and salt) can cause, in certain cases, irreversible changes that usually degrade the mechanical performance of the laminate ^{1,2}.

In most organic matrices water absorption is relatively low (0.5-1.5%). Under favourable conditions (time, temperature) the presence of water within the laminate can cause in some matrices hydrolysis, plasticisation and reduction of heat distortion temperature of the resin which may affect mechanical performance of a laminate. Similarly, frozen laminate with higher moisture content can experience severe stresses which may result in delamination or stress cracking due to water expansion.

Solar radiation (heat and UV) may affect unprotected FRP laminate via several mechanisms of which all, like above, lead to reduction of mechanical properties. In case of lower temperature cured polyesters, "excessive" heat and thermal cycling can cause both, thermal instability and thermal fatigue of the laminate. UV radiation may cause chalk-like surface appearance as a result of chemical bond breakage in matrix resin.

In the presence of salt water galvanic corrosion can occur if carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) composite is physically in contact with metal ¹³.

3.3. Mechanical Properties

The test methods for FRP materials have been developed primarily for the aerospace industry. Some may not be applicable to the marine industry because much of the vessels structure, such as hull, parts of the deck and bulkheads, receive multiaxial loads. The standardised test procedures established by the American Society for Testing Materials (ASTM) and the Suppliers of Advanced Composite Materials Association (SACMA), generally used for FRP composite characterisation, are all uniaxial tests. Therefore design optimisation including safety factors is difficult until a set of tests, which will yield the right type of information, is developed for the marine industry ².

Because of their orthotropic characteristics, composite materials exhibit very complex failure mechanisms under static and fatigue loading. There are basically four failure mechanisms which affect composite materials as a result of cyclic stresses in a laminate; matrix cracking, delamination, fibre fracture and interfacial debonding. Additionally, in sandwich structures debonding of skin from the core is possible. The different failure modes combined with the inherent orthotropies, complex stress fields and overall non-linear behaviour of composites severally limit our ability to understand the true nature of fatigue ^{1,2}.

Behaviour of FRP composite materials subjected to impact at high loading rates is, in general, poorly understood because analytical methods are rather crude at present. This is yet another important parameter to be considered since the introduction of FRP laminates and sandwich construction has generally led to faster boats and thus increased the importance of impact performance ^{1,2}.

3.4. Design and Engineering Aspects

The mechanics of composite materials are quite different to metallic materials which, for design purposes, are generally considered to be isotropic. Most composites are orthotropic and this leads to different theories of structural analysis compared to metals. The approach used to determine analytically the properties of laminates include micromechanics and macromechanics. A lack of knowledge and understanding of these methods of analysis leads to improper evaluation and use of composites in marine applications. These methods must also predict the correct failure modes in order to give reliable estimates of strength.

There is increasing pressure to automate marine composite fabrication to improve efficiencies, reduce volatile emissions and reduce costs. In the future, innovative processes such as resin transfer moulding and a vacuum assisted open mould resin transfer process will be increasingly used. Modular construction of composite structures is also likely to increase. The modular concept will enable more automated processes to be used in fabricating individual components requiring only joining operations to be performed.

Joining techniques for shock resistance of adhesively bonded T-joints need to be improved. Future developments in this field will continue as shock resistance requirements increase. For bolted joints, maximum joint efficiency obtainable in GRP composites is estimated to be ~45-50% compared with ~70% for metal joints. Furthermore, composites are likely to be increasingly used in combination with metals (for example, GRP superstructures and metal hulls) and improved methods of joining composites to metals will be required ¹.

3.5. Other Factors

Apart from exceptional situations where advantages of the composite materials are at a premium, such as MCMVs and competition sporting boats and yachts, the reduced cost of ownership is the main criterion for the use of composites in the marine industry. The total life cycle cost entails material and construction expense including service life charges of repair and maintenance. In cost analysis, increased operational effectiveness for the same expenditure or increased safety should also be considered when deciding whether to build a marine structure in composites or metal. In some cases the initial cost of the structure may be greater than for metal, the operational efficiency through reduced maintenance and repair costs, however, may be lower. The lack of reliable cost estimation and modelling techniques for determining the cost of ownership for composite structures is seen as a restrictive factor in their marine usage. Unless it can be shown that the use of composites result in cost benefits, without impairing performance and safety, there will always be a reluctance to depart from metal structures.

With regard to composite materials development, various health regulations require ever decreasing permissible exposure limits (PEL) to solvents, synthetic mineral fibres, dust etc. in the workplace which will inevitably force manufacturers, for example, to alter formulations based on hazardous solvents ¹⁴ (ie. current PEL to styrene in Denmark and Sweden is 25 ppm and is expected to be reduced further). Consequently, employers will have to adjust their work practices in using fibres for production of small components. For large structures, the technologies for composite manufacture, especially in the field of pultrusion, are rapidly solving PEL in fabrication processes.

Tough new European Community (EC) directives, expected by mid-1990s, will force manufacturers to fabricate parts from recyclable materials. As a result, the UK is conducting a study of methods and problems in recycling advanced materials including composites used in the marine industry ¹⁵. In Japan, a large scale project is underway to establish a practical waste recycling program for bulk FRP waste, such as expended marine vessels. In the past, a standard procedure to minimise "GRP pollution" was to reduce FRP to small fragments which were then buried. New technologies, can recover oil, phthalic acid and some processes can produce porous glass and SiC whiskers ¹⁶. To recycle thermosets, scientists in the US have developed reversible epoxies cured with crosslinking agents which allow bond cleavage thus rendering the resin completely soluble for re-crosslinking. Recycling reinforced thermoplastic composites is a much simpler and cheaper task. For example, 900 kg of nylon can be recycled into an injection moulding compound for 66 cents/kg¹⁷.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper an attempt has been made to briefly present composite materials and their use in the marine industry covering scientific, technological and other factors. For future growth of marine composites progress will need to be made in areas of fire resistant resins, composite characterisation, design and development of economic fabrication processes for large structures. Designers will need to become more familiar with properties of, and design criteria for composites in order to exploit advantages of these new materials. Finally, a new cadre of engineers and workers with technical skills and understanding of composites, will need to be developed in shipyards to implement new processes for fabrication of large primary composite structures. These complex tasks are prerequisite investments for widespread global acceptance of composites which could also significantly benefit from an organised cooperative effort employing the combined talents of materials suppliers, composite manufacturers, the marine and aircraft industries, and academia.

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